

BUYING PATTERN TOWARDS TWO - WHEELERS - A STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO MAYILADUTHURAI TOWN

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Buyer behaviour is the cornerstone 'of marketing strategy. Firms must understand buyer behaviour to achieve the objectives of customer satisfaction. Buyer's mind is called "Black Box". Inputs are processed in his mind and buyers responses are the outputs through the influence from various factors. The objectives of the marketers to make this output a favourable one i.e., the decision to buy. Buyer behaviour is an orderly process whereby the buyer interacts with his environments for making a purchase decision on products.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The convenience seeking behaviour of the consumers create both growth and innovation in many industries. Irrespective of Global financial crisis, most of the Indian industries are sailing against the wind. Technological Developments in transportation and in allied industries make the movement of people from one place to another place a pleasing one. The growth of two — wheeler industries has been contributing significantly in the sophisticated journey experience. But human mind is not fully satisfied with the provision available around the world. On the one side the developments in the two wheeler industries is growing day by day on the next side the expectations of the two - wheeler users are increasing unboundly.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The following are the specific objectives of the study;

- To know the factors influencing the two - wheelers buyer's purchasing decisions.
- To draw the opinion of respondents about the new models and facilities available with the

two - wheelers.

- To offer suitable suggestions and findings of the present study.

METHODOLOGY

The information have been collected both from primary and secondary data. The primary data have been collected from the selected 75 respondents by administering a structured questionnaire which contained the purposive 25 questions. The secondary data have ' been gathered from relevant, newspapers, journals, magazines and from the Internet.

LIMITATIONS

The following are the limitations of the study;

1. The present study covered the period only during 2016 - 2017.
2. The sample size 75 has been selected based on the convenience sampling methods. So this study is subject to the limitations of convenience sampling method.

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Male	70	87.5
Female	10	12.5
Age		
Below 20 years	10	12.15
21 – 30 years	53	66.25
31 – 40 years	10	12.5
41 – 50 years	5	6.25
Above 50 years	2	2.5
Total	80	100
Education qualification		
Up to S.S.L.C	20	2.5
Higher Sec.	10	12.5
Diploma	10	12.5
Under Graduate	30	37.5
Post Graduate	10	12.5
Occupation		

Agriculture	10	12.5
Business Man	30	37.5
Employment	30	37.5
Professional	10	12.5
Income		
Upto Rs.10,000	25	31.25
10000 – 15000	30	37.5
Above Rs.15000	25	31.25
Total	80	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shows the demographic profile of the sample respondents for this study. The table clearly indicates the sample respondents of 75. The Demographic Profile which specify the Gender, Age, Education, Occupation and Income level of the sample respondents.

PREFERENCE ON OTHER BRAND

Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Hero	15	18.75
T.V.S	10	12.5
Bajaj	15	18.75
Yamaha	10	12.5
Royal Enfield	5	6.25
Honda	25	31.25
Total	80	100

Source : Primary Data

The above table depicted the preference of particular brand two – wheeler holder on other branded two – wheelers. 18.75% of the Honda holders like to have Honda than their present two – wheelers brand. Around of the non hero – Honda holding respondents wished to hold hero branded bikes.

FACTOR INFLUENCING THE PURCHASE

Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Personal Transport	44	55
Fashionable	11	13.75
Official Use	25	31.25
Total	80	100

Source : Primary Data

The above table has attempted to explain the actual need which motivated the respondents towards the purchase of two – wheelers. On the same table 3.13, around 55% of the respondents have decided to purchase the two – wheelers for their personal transport, 13.75% of the respondents said that they wanted to hold the two – wheelers just as a fashion symbol.

OPINION ON MILEAGE

Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Excellent	14	17.5
Good	66	82.5
Poor	Nil	Nil
Total	80	100

Source : Primary Data

The above table has presented the respondents opinion on their two – wheelers. On the same table , 82.5% of the respondents felt 'Good' with reference to the mileage aspect of their of their two – wheelers. Only 17.5% of the respondents said that they had 'Excellent' experience with the mileage of their two – wheelers.

BRAND PREFERENCE FOR SECOND HAND VALUE

Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Honda	9	11.25
T.V.S	49	61.25
Bajaj	11	13.75
Yamaha	11	13.75
Total	80	100

Source : Primary Data

The current table throws light on the preference of two – wheelers based on their second hand value. According to the table around 61.25% of the respondents are casting their vote towards TVS brand two – wheelers for the maximum second hand value. Interestingly no respondents considered the TVS brand bikes have significant second hand value.

PERFERENCE OF SELF START BIKES

Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	57	71.25
No	23	28.75
Total	80	100

Source : Primary Data

In the Modern two – wheelers market, products are introduced with new features to attract the mass customer. The self start bike is one of such innovations. According to the above table, 71.25% . of the respondents preferred self – start type two – wheelers and 28.75% of the respondents not shown interest on these type of bikes.

PROVISION OF ALLOY WHEEL

Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	9	11.25
No	71	88.75
Total	80	100

Source : Primary Data

According to the above table, only 2 out of 75 respondents have alloy wheel bikes and 88.75% of the respondents have no alloy wheel bikes. So, it is concluded from the above table that most of the respondents have no alloy wheel bikes. The reason may be due to the inconvenience associated with this type of bikes.

FINDINGS:

- It is clear that very few female respondents who preferred this type of two – wheelers for transport purpose. Out of 80 sample respondents 70 are male members and 10 members belong to female respondents.
- ➔ Most of the respondents have been represented 21 – 30 years age group people.
- ➔ 18.75% of the Honda holders like to have Honda than their present two – wheelers brand.

Around of the non hero – Honda holding respondents wished to hold hero branded bikes.

- only 2 out of 75 respondents have alloy wheel bikes and 88.75% of the respondents have no alloy wheel bikes. So, it is concluded from the above table that most of the respondents have no alloy wheel bikes.

SUGGESTIONS

- In the Competitive world, the customer get full knowledge about the product then only he purchase it. So the manufacturers of two wheelers can identify the needs of the buyer.
- Most of the buyer prefer safety of the two wheeler. Hence the manufacturer should concentrate the safety sections like Brake, clutch, weight of the Bike, etc.
- The manufacturer should concentrate the mileage of the bike because most of the buyer expect this one.
- The manufacture should reduce the price of the two wheelers it will leads to meet out the competition.

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